

INCLUSIVE HEALTH CARE IN INDIA: EXISTING POLICIES, PRACTICES, AND ROAD AHEAD

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Abstract

Health is the most important component not only for human survival but also for the effective growth of culture, civilization, and the economy. An imbalance in the body's ecosystem leads to a health crisis and warrants an effective solution.

The welfare nation has a pivotal role to play in providing healthcare to all, not in letters but in spirit. Following decolonization, all developing countries, including India, adopted a policy of ensuring healthcare for all their citizens, regardless of economic background. However, the issue of providing quality health care remains more in papers rather than in the ground reality.

With liberalisation and the corporate health care system, the burden of healthcare for the rich has been a little bit offloaded from government responsibility, but we still have a long way to go. In this study, the author made an effort to understand the pressing needs of healthcare for all, the healthcare facility divides between urban and rural areas, and the types of healthcare schemes and policy framework available for all sections of people.

Keywords: *Comprehensive policy, health policy, public health, health education*

Introduction

As a welfare state, the healthcare policy of India was founded on the recommendations of **Bhore** Committee report of 1946. It outlines that healthcare is one of the primary responsibilities of the state, being an integrated one with both preventive and curative action under a single umbrella. This further emphasized the availability of ancillary facilities like drugs, biological items, surgical products, and being managed by full-time skilled personnel. In a post-independent scenario, getting healthcare is considered as a fundamental right, and medical personnel need to provide immediate and emergency medical service without demanding any type of fees or delaying the matter under the pretext of medico-legal issues.

Though the policies are quite ideal and lofty to read, in reality, there is a huge disparity in getting proper health care. This disparity is clearly distinguishable with economic, educational, and demographic divides. Rural healthcare in India is in a mess. Many of its citizens are neither aware of the facilities available nor of the financial support mechanisms.

Post-Independent Healthcare Evolution in India

The Medical Education Conference (1955) first to recommend establishing the Department of Preventive and Social Medicine in medical colleges nationwide, better termed as community medicine. This concept was incorporated into the medical education curriculum and students were assigned to take up preventive and healthcare initiatives both in rural and urban areas as a part of partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of a medical degree.

In 1961, the **Mudaliar Committee** ratified this by recommending schools of public health in every state to train medical officers, paramedical staff, maternity and child welfare workers, public health department personnel, sanitary workers, epidemiologists, nutritionists, and other field workers.

The **Shrivastava Committee Report in 1975** observed that the medical education was primarily urban-oriented and lacked in training manpower towards nutrition, maternity, and childcare in rural surroundings, and a large section of the population is deprived of accessibility to doctors. He emphasized more on community medicine and integrating family planning with medical education. It pointed out that the role of a general practitioner goes beyond just treating sickness, with extended role of becoming a mentor to compliment health care with social and cultural fabric of the community he/ she serves.

In 1977, India launched the **Re-Orientation of Medical Education (ROME)** scheme across the country, where medical colleges were encouraged to adopt preventive and curative health care at first in community development blocks, then covering the entire district. The objective of this scheme was to be a bridge by linking medical colleges to rural communities to provide quality healthcare and acclimatise medical students on rural healthcare system. But the spread of this concept was limited as most of the medical colleges were traditionally focused on a curative approach of healthcare with an urban orientation.

With constitution of an **Expert Committee for Health Manpower Planning, Production and Management(1985)** a process was initiated to understand ground realities on the disparity of existing manpower to projected manpower catering to primary and secondary(intermediate) healthcare operation / management. Further to that it recommends the typical skill based educational institutions and ancillary facilities to produce suitable manpower to bridge the gap.

In a chain effect Expert Committee on Public Health System (1996) was formed under the aegis of Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Subsequent to that in 1997 an independent commission named Voluntary Health Association of India (VHAI) was formed. The basic recommendations of all these bodies were to strengthen the public health awareness through education and training. They find a clear shortage in public health schools and inadequate facility in existing schools.

A deeper look into public health was made in **Regional Conference on Public Health in South East Asia** in the 21st Century at Calcutta. A comprehensive public health system was proposed to be brought into action. This is better known as **Calcutta Declaration**. This declaration primarily focused on developing public health as an integral part of healthcare system. It emphasized the role to be proactive, and developing a career structure starting from district level going up to national level. Along with this effective networking, proper training and adequate research was also recommended with blending of information technology. Consequent to this in 2006 Public Health Foundation of India (PHFI) was launched in 2006. The primary objective of this is to bridge the gap between demand and supply of trained healthcare personnel in India.

Then came the National Health Policy (NHP) of 2015. It was a global compulsion to move towards universal health coverage. The basic motto of National Health Policy is to ensure that good health leads to productivity which ultimately gives rise to economic growth. And economic growth must be leveraged to better healthcare. The NHP is a guiding force for prioritising government's role in health system mechanism in a holistic manner. It included investment for health care, augmenting and financing healthcare services, prevention initiative, and promotion of good health, technological accessibility, and medical pluralism, knowledge management on health, healthcare financing and legislation for health. This NHP is implemented to take care of following differentiation on context.

Firstly, Health Priorities are changing. As a result of focused action over the last decade, we are projected to attain the Millennium Development Goals with respect to maternal and child mortality. Maternal mortality now accounts for 0.55% of all deaths and 4% of all female deaths in the 15 to 49-year age group. This is still 46,500 maternal deaths too many, and demands that the commitments to further reduction must not flag.

The second important change in context is the emergence of a robust health care industry growing at 15% compound annual growth rate (CAGR).

Thirdly, the incidence of catastrophic expenditure due to health care costs was growing and being estimated to be one of the major contributors to poverty. The fourth and final change in context was that of economic growth which has increased the fiscal capacity available.

Therefore, the country needed a new health policy that would be responsive to these contextual changes. Other than these objective factors, the political will to ensure universal access to affordable healthcare services in an assured mode – the promise of Health Assurance – became an important catalyst for the framing of a New Health Policy.

With this backdrop, the New Health Policy 2015 was formulated with the following salient features[33]

➤ Equity:

Health care would be a state responsibility, and it must ensure equitable extension of facilities to all its citizens. This includes ensuring the absence of disparity on account of sex, economic background, caste, religion, or any forms of social exclusion, and geographical barriers.

➤ Universality:

The system of healthcare service must be non-discriminatory and strive to prevent exclusions on social or economic grounds.

➤ Patient Centric Qualitative Health Care:

Health Care services would be effective, safe, and convenient, provided with dignity and confidentiality. The facilities across all sectors of the service need to be assessed, certified, and incentivized to ensure the quality

➤ Inclusive Partnerships:

As providing a massive population of India is a herculean task, the government does need active support from social organizations, corporates, NGOs, and academic institutes to make it feasible and vibrant.

➤ Pluralism:

There are various systems of medicine like allopathy, homeopathy, ayurveda, unani, and Shiv Shidant. The patient needs to be facilitated to take up any of the systems of healthcare as per convenience and preference. The government must ensure effective regulation, research, and spread of all systems of healthcare facilities, thereby ensuring medical pluralism.

- **Subsidiarity:**
Since responsiveness is the primary focus of any healthcare system, effective delegation of authority should be ensured for effective operational management and a decentralized system of administration.
- **Accountability:**
Transparency in service, diagnostic investigation and financial transaction is very much important to make the health care system corruption-free, accountable and logically affordable.
- **Professionalism, Integrity, and Ethics:**
Doctors, paramedical staff, and health workers need to perform their work with the highest level of professionalism and integrity; they deserve to be supported by a system and regulatory environment complementary to this.
- **Learning and Adaptive System:**
Health care is a dynamic activity, and organizations involved in this profession are bound to upgrade and adapt to changing needs. The process of implementation is the experience in the health care system and requires a careful approach with alignment from national and international partners.
- **Affordability:**
Along with equity, affordability is also an important parameter towards achieving quality health care. There is a thumb rule. The health care costs of a household should neither exceed 10% of its total monthly consumption expenditures nor 40% of its nonfood consumption expenditure. Anything beyond this is catastrophic and unacceptable.

The Economics of Healthcare

In Indian context, there is a change in the disease pattern and non-communicable illness are on the rise. The increase in the lifestyle disease led to sharp increase in the cost of healthcare expenditure in the recent years.

Studies have revealed that the share of out of pocket spending (OOPS) has increased from 4 percent to 7 percent in the past two decades (**Hoonda, 2015**) and per capita expenditure for availing the healthcare services has also been increased. It was around 10 rupees per person in 2000 and it has been increased to staggering 75 rupees in 2012. The burden of treatment is still

more acute on part of the poor families as 20 percent of their total household expenditure go to healthcare treatment (**Chowdari S 2011**) as 70 percent of the health care expenditure is borne by the sick individual or his/her family. This kind of situation is forcing many households to compromise on food and non-food items. For instance, overall, monthly average consumption level per individual has been reduced to 7.4 rupees due to high spending on healthcare.

Substantial proportion of both rural (47 percent) and urban (31 percent) households depend on loan or sale of property to settle the hospital bills (WHO). As per the WHO estimation, a little more than 3 percent of Indians fall under the BPL bracket due to high healthcare payments. According to an estimation close to 95 million people became economically weak in 2014 due to high medical expenditure. These facts and figures proclaim that the cost of healthcare treatment has become as one of the negative catalyst of economy leading to aggravating the poverty of India.

In this backdrop, health insurance has been a light of home and gaining importance in the recent years. It safeguards the individuals from the fear of high OOPS and helps to get better healthcare treatments. Common services which are available to the consumers in various health insurance policies are settlement or reimbursement of medical bills, cashless hospitalization, medical treatment in the best hospitals, policy renewal benefits, group insurance benefits etc. (**Sonal, 2015**).

But a significant proportion of the population, both in rural and urban areas, do not have health insurance, and those who have registered or purchased the insurance product, the majority of them are either enrolled under the government-sponsored schemes or employer-supported schemes.

With respect to coverage, it is more prevalent among the urban population than the rural. The government of India and the state governments are committed to safeguarding the poor and the weaker sections of the community from the catastrophic healthcare expenditure and to ensure universal health care by launching various health insurance schemes at different points of time, which are suitable for different population sub-groups. We have explored this aspect of healthcare assistance and its spread among the Indian population

A. Illness Coverage by Insurance Companies

As it can be seen in Figure 1, a majority of the population under insurance coverage is not covered by all diseases. And unfortunately, a majority do not have any idea of the coverage.

B. Health Insurance Awareness

It is observed that the awareness of health insurance is higher in urban areas as compared to rural areas (Figure 2).

But going by figure 3, the awareness of health insurance is better as income progresses, irrespective of rural or urban dwelling.

C. Actual Insurance Coverage

Awareness is one thing. It is important to know how many persons are getting or actually using insurance for illness coverage.

Confirming to awareness more household in urban dwelling are covered by the health insurance (Figure 4).

Again, as shown in Figure 5, irrespective of rural or urban, the insurance coverage increases as there is growth in income. And this divide is negligible in low low-income group, but very sharp in the high-income group.

As per profession, the salaried class population is far ahead in the matter of coverage, the least covered being business class people. And in all income categories urban population is better covered than the rural population (Figure 7).

The second aspect of insurance is related to knowledge on insurance coverage of diseases. It has been found that 31 percent of insured persons do not have any idea on the disease covered and 38 percent have some information. Only a minority population of 31 percent have full information on insurance coverage of diseases (Figure 8).

Going by preference for healthcare insurance is concerned ESI is first preferred followed by Central government scheme. The least preferred is Mediclaim (Figure 9).

Conclusion

All these indicate that there is a long way to go as far as healthcare is concerned and its subsequent financial burden. Furthermore, the mechanism of healthcare insurance and its business model are not so prevalent in the Indian context.

As depicted in Figure 10, the primary reason for not having insurance is a lack of knowledge. Hence, adequate exposure and publicity must be given to make health care universal and affordable.

Liberalism opened the way for public-private partnerships to achieve health for all. This is also required to meet the needs of a larger population. Health policy and governance expect effective state regulation and dedicated bureaucracy. Additionally, Comprehensive knowledge on health insurance and its utilization can only help in improving the coverage of insurance among the people, including BPL households, and save the people from health-related financial shocks.

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